

WORK IN THE DIRECTION OF UZAUTO COMPONENTS

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Annotation

This article covers the work carried out in the direction of UZAUTO components and the optimization of production processes and modernization processes.

Keywords: UZAUTO, National Company, Network, car, modernization.

UzAuto Motors aims to become the leader of the automotive industry within the CIS countries and intends to produce up to a million cars”, “a new autogigant may appear in the CIS” – news under the same title is often featured in World internet publications. Of course, on the ground of such recognition lies not only the numbers, but also the enormous labor of all sectors in Uzbekistan.

As a result of the reforms carried out by the head of state and the implementation of all internal processes and a new strategy for the development of Uzbekistan, which serves to increase the prestige of our country in the international arena, the automotive industry, which has accumulated priorities such as expanding and modernizing production, developing science and technology, as well as creating

Due to the optimization and modernization of production processes, UzAuto Motors has achieved a historical record-that is, since 2016, production has grown by 269%. The introduction of new technologies into the production process, equipment upgrades and an increase in personnel skills made UzAuto Motors, which is considered the leader in Central Asia, a giant car manufacturer in the CIS.

Today, UzAuto Motors has launched the production of only the most modern cars, in particular, Chevrolet Tracker and Onix cars. For this, more than 5 thousand engineers are involved, part of which are graduates of the Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent. As a result of the involvement of foreign and domestic specialists in 200 existing enterprises in Uzbekistan, with their support, the production of 1.5 thousand details for Chevrolet Tracker and Onix cars was established. In order to organize the production of Chevrolet Tracker and Onix cars in Uzbekistan, 12 new localization projects were carried out by OJSC “Uzavtosanoat”, including new factories and high-tech production lines with a total cost of \$ 312 million were lowered. The launch of new production facilities will make it possible to create about 4.5 thousand new jobs.

The new cars are based on the Global Emerging Markets (GEM) global Platform, which was introduced at the UzAuto Motors plant, which means to establish the production of several types of cars without additional engineering solutions. \$ 427.6 million was invested in the development of this project.

The production of cast iron parts was established at the Kova foundry, which was launched in the Andijan region. In order to master new types of high-value added products, all the important steps in metal processing were involved, including advanced, latest-class techniques and technologies necessary in the process of smelting, casting, molding and high-precision

mechanical processing. In an enterprise with a capacity of 18 thousand tons of products per year, there is an opportunity to reduce the import of spare parts by \$ 21 million, increasing the added value of raw materials by 10 times.

Within the framework of the localization program, the UzAuto Network Enterprises were guided by the production of radiators with a modern engine cooling system, a multifunctional steering wheel with a Joyson Safety Systems car control feature, as well as an airbag, as well as plastic tanks operating on the basis of modern and unique technologies. In addition, the production of side windows for Chevrolet Onix and Tracker cars was mastered at UzKoram-Co LLC. For the first time, the production and processing of plastic and rubber parts in a modern way, including using the extrusion method, was admired on the road. Also, ultrasonic welding of plastic parts and pressure casting of two-component plastics were introduced, which makes it possible to achieve high Hermeticism, high indicators of shock or vibration absorption.

The modernization of the plant also included the process of manufacturing car body parts by hot stamping. The establishment of the only fully automated metal processing Tsex in Central Asia by hot stamping at the UzSungwoo plant made it possible to replace imports of nearly 214.5 billion soums, in exchange for the production of 20 types of domestic components for Chevrolet Tracker and Onix models. Developed using the latest technologies installed at UzSungwoo, the metal hot processing line is equipped with metal cutting, hot pressing and laser cutting equipment from leading world suppliers, allowing to produce 2.4 million pieces of metal products and saving investments in exchange for reducing the necessary equipment by up to 5 times. The introduction of innovative production technologies directly affected the production capacities of the UzAuto Motors plant in Asaka as well. In addition to the main production units, the company has established the laser welding process, which, in comparison with other welding methods, is aimed at high accuracy, corrosion resistance and welding seam in the production process, as well as aesthetic, high energy saving level and environmental protection in production.

Of course, the projects implemented represent that Uzbekistan has all the conditions and opportunities for further development of auto industry and bringing the volume of car production to 500 thousand units per year, and in the future to a million units.

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